

There's a Grizzly Bear in Sector 7: Emotional triggers in an online GIS-based information system for management and safety of natural heritage parks in Canada

Milena Radzikowska, MDes Faculty of Communication Studies, Mount Royal College, Calgary, Canada (403) 440-8941, mradzikowska@mtroyal.ca

Patricia M. Derbyshire, MA Bissett School of Business, Mount Royal College, Calgary, Canada (403) 440-6397, pderbyshire@mtroyal.ca

Barbara McNicol, PhD Department of Earth Sciences, Faculty of Science & Technology, Mount Royal College, Calgary, Canada (403) 440-6175, bmcnicol@mtroyal.ca

Chris Irish, Senior Student Department of Physical Education & Recreation Studies, Faculty of Health & Community Studies, Mount Royal College, Calgary, Canada (403) 440-6896 chrisirish@hotmail.com

Matt Bouchard, Masters Student Humanities Computing, Office of Interdisciplinary Studies, University of Alberta, Edmonton, Canada (780) 909-1295 matt.bouchard@gmail.com

Jacob Quinlan, Student Faculty of Communication Studies, Mount Royal College, Calgary, Canada (403) 440-6958 jacob.quinlan@gmail.com

Stan Ruecker, PhD Humanities Computing, Department of English and Film Studies, University of Alberta, Edmonton, Canada (780) 914-6372 sruecker@ualberta.ca

Abstract

Online public information systems for the management of natural heritage parks pose a number of interesting design challenges, in the sense that the emotional responses of the two primary stakeholder groups – park visitors and park managers – are not necessarily congruent with one another. On the one hand, both managers and visitors need to know what is going on in the park, since conflicting activities by different groups could pose hazards, and interactions between animals and humans need to be kept under control. On the other hand, as Appleton (1976) points out, hazard is attractive to people, and knowing where to find it may result in increased numbers of parks users taking risks that are contrary to the intentions of the parks managers.

In this paper, we discuss the iterative design of an online geographic information system (GIS) called UMa. The goal of the system is to minimize negative emotional triggers common to

interactions on the natural landscape and to encourage sustainable decision making by providing potential park visitor groups with frequently updated data on park usage, including wildlife/animal movement patterns.

Of particular concern for park managers is park use by school teachers and students, since encounters between school groups and the ecosystem, and school groups and other visitors carry a high-risk potential. For example, periodic permissions are issued to hunters so that they can enter a park and cull overpopulated herds. Knowing where the hunters are is important, since risk is increased if the same area is being occupied, for instance, by a school outing. In this case, providing information directly may be the best course, since teachers will not intentionally seek out risk for their students.

Wildlife and people, however, are a different situation; bears are a good example of a case where risks can be introduced by the information system. In an earlier design, the system would show a small icon of a moving bear, placed precisely on the map. The problem is that some parks visitors are attracted to bears, whether in ignorance of the possible danger or because of it. The result was that rather than warning people from the area, the information was an attraction.

With the first implemented version of UMa we are working with park managers and primary school educators to explore two hypotheses. Our primary hypothesis is that by designing a useful and appropriate on-line park management system, we can encourage visitors to make sustainable decisions regarding their park visit – decisions that will minimize certain negative impacts on the park and each other, resulting in positive experiences for the visitors. Our secondary hypothesis is that in order to mediate emotional triggers for different park visitor groups we will need to present information at varying levels of granularity. As the system addresses the needs of hunters, for example, we will have to reconsider how abstract and opaque we make the system's information design.

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Introduction

In Canada, there exists a diversity of protected spaces that fit the six global categories identified by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) (Bishop Et. al., 2004). This diversity ensures that within Canadian parks there is a continuum of human use that extends from complete protection of the natural heritage site to high-density visitor activities. Examples of protected areas include wildlife reserves that allow only scientific use, while high-density sites include provincial recreational areas that allow all-terrain vehicles and hunting activities. Canada's provincial park systems (managed from within provincial governmental jurisdiction) fit the category of high human use and, consequently, high conflict conservation areas. There were over 13 million visits to Canada's national parks between 2006 and 2007, with over 6 million visitors to Alberta parks. (http://www.pc.gc.ca/docs/pc/attend/table1_E.asp). Alberta parks span more than 500 sites, covering 27,525 square kilometers (<http://www.finance.alberta.ca/publications/budget/budget2008/tourism.pdf>).

The park's stakeholders include, in broad categories, humans and the ecosystem. The human stakeholders involve: educational groups both large and small (K-12: Kindergarten to post-secondary); tourists; local residents (who can include hunters and Aboriginal communities); commercial operators; researchers; industry; and the Government. The ecosystem stakeholders involve air, water, soil, vegetation, natural hazards, and wildlife.

Canada's parks are vast, popular, and difficult to manage. Most park managers rely on a manually generated permitting system to know who is on the landscape, and two-way communication with visitors is currently limited. On the front lines, there are very few technology-based solutions that generate accurate and timely information regarding park use. In many instances park managers don't know what kind of visitors are in their park, how many visitors are on the park's grounds at a particular time, and what kinds of activities they are engaged in. They also have little knowledge as to how visitors are impacting the ecosystem, and managing and mitigating emotional triggers, including risk, poses a substantial challenge.

In consultation with a team representing a provincial park in Kananaskis Country and a team of K-12 educators from Calgary, we are iteratively designing and developing an online geographic information system (GIS) called UMa. Our goal is to help enable park managers and visitors to make sustainable decisions regarding park use and enjoyment; thus, helping to reduce certain emotional triggers, minimize risk to people and wildlife, and preserve the ecological health of habitats in Alberta's parks and protected areas.

Background & Relevant Literature

In preparation for the interface design phase of the project, we examined two main sources for potential conflict within the park. First, conflicts that may emerge from negative visitor-ecosystem interaction. Second, conflicts that may emerge from visitor-visitor interactions. Managing potential conflicts between these stakeholders is critical towards satisfying the dual mandate established by park management: to enable the enjoyment of parks by visitors; and to support the conservation of the ecological systems within the park.

Emotional Triggers & Managing Potential Visitor-Ecosystem Conflicts

The concept of emotional triggers is derived from the study of emotional arousal and attachment in the field of psychology. Easterbrook's (1959) cue utilization theory predicted that high levels of arousal will lead to attention narrowing (i.e., a decrease in the range of cues from the stimulus and its environment to which an organism is sensitive). Thus, in the blink of an eye, attention focuses on the arousing details (cues) of the stimulus, so that information central to the source of the emotional arousal will be encoded while peripheral details may not.

Emotional triggers also precipitate what are perceived to be an instantaneous shift in mood. Kellert (1996) noted that human interactions with wildlife often, "evoke a strong, primarily emotional register in most people, provoking feelings of intense pleasure, even awe."(p.15) In their analysis of human dimensions of wildlife interaction, Newsome et al. (2005) also cite a powerful psychological dimension of bonding and attachment, as with mother and child, which motivates and mobilizes both mental and behavioural activities of interaction. It is known through Kellert's observations, for example, that there is a high level of arousal and attraction to both the large and the 'cute and cuddly.' The more young, small, soft, fluffy and playful seeming the wildlife, the greater the level of our attraction and need to interact and bond. (p.17)

Tate & Pelton (1983), among others, question the role of folklore and the teddy bear syndrome (i.e., the iconic role of the animated and toy bear) as the basis of emotional triggers and consequent negative human behaviours of crowding, feeding and photo-crowding bears which lead to aggressive wildlife responses and visitor-wildlife conflict.

Finally, Orams (2002) notes the rise of nature conservation in popular culture and media at the same time that opportunities in nature, for most part, are in decline (p.287), providing a fascinating look at triggers associated with 'provisioning' wildlife. Based on three competing philosophical perspectives he posits that our inclination 'to feed' is guided by either: (1) a view that animals are subordinate and thus humans assert a right to utilize wildlife for human benefit regardless of consequence; (2) that one may see animals as equal or equivalent status to humans and therefore be afforded agency and care and/or; (3) a view of wildlife as reverent, spiritual where offering should be made. (p.289)

In each study, the ubiquity of the human-wildlife interaction and associated dangers in national parks and preserves throughout the world is noted. Emotional triggers are complex, are rooted in history and emotion. There are multiple sources of triggers beyond this brief overview that present for each stakeholder group, all of which lead to particular behaviours.

One of the most developed landscapes in North America where grizzly bears still survive is within the Central Rockies Ecosystem (CRE), including Banff, Yoho, and Kootenay National Parks, and adjoining parks including Kananaskis (www.canadianrockies.net/Grizzly/).

According to the Grizzly Bear Alliance, there are fewer than 500 grizzly bears in Alberta – less than half the number that was reported in 2002 (www.grizzlybearalliance.org). Between 1971 and 1996, human actions accounted for the greatest proportion of all grizzly bear deaths within the CRE (Byron, 1998), while between 1960 and 1998, grizzly bears were the cause of 42 human deaths or serious injuries (Herrero and Higgins, 2003).

Despite educational, publicity and awareness efforts to dissuade people from interacting with wildlife, wildlife paparazzi (i.e., those who actively seek out encounters) are a real concern for parks managers (Figure 1). Interactions, individual or group, responsible and aware or a novice to the Canadian wilderness experience, can result in emotionally-charged experiences – on the part of those participating in the encounter and/or the encounter's observers – that range from the mundane, escalating to the extreme and potentially life-threatening.

Figure 1. A bear paparazzi photographing a black bear and her cub.
(Photo courtesy of Larry Halverson, Kootenay National Park.)

Visitor-Visitor Interaction and the Potential for Conflict

Hunting, with a valid hunting license, is permitted in wildland provincial parks. There are also limited hunting seasons in some provincial recreation areas (Alberta Provincial Parks and Recreation Areas Regulations, 2003) during which periodic permissions are issued so that hunters can enter a park and cull overpopulated herds.

However, parks and protected areas are also utilized by educators in Alberta during the fall, winter and spring seasons. Since hunters, teachers, and students may be in a given park area at the same time, interaction between the groups is likely. Knowing where the respective groups are located is important, because risk is increased if the same area is being occupied, for instance, by both the permitted hunter and a school outing.

Additional triggers for educators may therefore include, for example, accountabilities for risk management, planning and group management stressors, and curriculum delivery and outcomes pressures. Despite strong risk management programs for outdoor education in Alberta, K-12 educators seldom learn of other school groups on the landscape, with multiple large school groupings alone presenting potential recreational coping issues.

Recreational coping occurs when visitors experience stress or when so-called 'use densities' are perceived or experienced as being too great. For example, coping emerges in response to crowding and access, damage to sites, noise from others, even littering (Peden, 2004; Schuster, 2000). Recreational coping is thought to be a key factor in positive visitor experiences and affects social, biophysical and ecological health outcomes in outdoor recreational settings.

Negative effects, for instance, in Dinosaur Provincial Park, ecological concerns include: removal of fossil materials; cumulative impacts of hiking and scrambling on badland formations; removal of dead branches and trees by campers; and air quality problems created by burning campfires (http://www.pc.gc.ca/docs/pm-wh/rspm-whsr/rapports-reports/r2_e.asp).

Three main coping responses tend to occur with visitors: product-shifting, rationalization, and displacement (Hoss & Brunson, 2000; Johnson & Dawson, 2004; Manning & Vallaire, 2001). Product-shift occurs when visitors redefine their expectations based on actual on-site events (Shelby et al., 1988). Rationalization occurs when consistency between expectation and actual experience leads to the justification of stressful conditions (Festinger 1957; Hoss & Brunson, 2000). Finally, displacement is a response to use density where, quite simply, visitors seek to avoid others by either moving to a different site or area or by visiting at a different time (Manning & Vallaire, 2001).

Little has been documented on proactive or pre-visit strategies or resources and the consequent effects on group users in particular. The literature is also silent on the link between pre-visit strategies, recreational coping, the use of technology solutions or the efficacy of interface design and its effect on the promotion of stewardship behaviours. The following sections discuss the iterative process for the interface design, user feedback, client consultation and revisions to the prototype.

Framing the Project

Given the needs of park managers, our primary client and the needs of park users, our goal for the interface design project was to (a) identify and (b) mitigate potential emotional triggers experienced in the context of management and large group use of parks in Alberta, Canada through the design and realization of a web resource, initially for K-12 teachers.

In consultation with a management and parks team located in Kananaskis Country, key strategies are being pursued in the resource design that enable sustainable decision-making and user engagement with the ecological health of habitats in Alberta's parks and protected areas.

Sustainable decision-making: First, the resource aims to provide managers, staff and stewardship groups in the province with the means to collect and examine empirical data and improved information on the nature, use, and effects of large group use with park resources.

Recreational coping and user engagement: Second, the resource targets K-12 educators by providing the means to attain school group permits, promote sustainable decision-making and recreational coping.

The Iterative Interface Design – Methods & Processes

The project's research protocol draws upon a blend of action research and phenomenological frameworks using both qualitative and quantitative methods. McKernan (1987) frames action research as a type of grounded theory which embodies problem-solving, self reflective practice and an improvement mindset. Its validity is not based on a 'test of truth' common in social science but the extent to which actors can become more effective in and strategic about their work. Somekh (1995) adds that, "underpinning action research is a set of democratic values, which endow the action researcher with the right to take control of the research process and make decisions about the full range of methodological issues on the basis of careful judgment and contextual knowledge" (p.340).

The first phase of the project began in the fall of 2006. The academic project team at Mount Royal College consulted with key staff from the Alberta Government's Parks and Protected Areas (PPA) division and learned that little is understood about large group use and the effect of multiple groups on parks, protected areas systems and habitats overseen by the province.

We learned, for example, that while rules and regulations are posted via the web and group permits are applied for and issued, little data is collected on the nature of the group, numbers of group attendees, the nature of their visit or use, and the extent to which users experience intended outcomes or form valued relationships to our Provincial Parks as a consequence of their visits.

Because of the consultative approach with our client we were challenged to consider emotional triggers and the negative consequences of being overly transparent through design functionality. For the first time, the identification of known risk (i.e., the sighting and movement of bears) shifted to the necessary and rationalized masking of such hazards, which also rightly remains the purview of experienced parks managers and educators. This was our first exposure to the concept of wildlife paparazzi and the danger that functionality could create rather than mitigate.

UMa

UMa's core functionality lies in the Trip Planner (Figure 2) – a linear park visit booking system consisting of six steps: *Trips, Activities, Maps, Forms, Resources* and *Book Trip*. To get started, the user can modify or duplicate a previously-created trip, or create a new trip. Booking a trip involves selecting dates for the trip, activities to do while in the park, and the areas of the park best suited for those activities. Examples of activities include hiking, snow shoeing, and skiing. There are summer, winter, and year-round activities. Activities and areas are closely related but not all areas can support every activity.

Some users are familiar with the park, its areas and activities. They know what they want to do and where they want to do it. In contrast, some users new to the park are interested in learning what the park has to offer, then making an educated decision regarding their visit. However, neither group knows to what extent the park is being used in a particular area for a given time period.

For example, if a teacher plans to take his group of thirty Grade 6 students to ski in the park on Friday, he is unlikely to know that another teacher has already planned to take her Grade 11 students to ski in the same area and on the same day. Based on a pre-selected day, UMa makes suggestions as to the areas and/or activities best available for a booking. If the Grade 11 teacher already made her booking, when the Grade 6 teacher tries to book the same activity on the same day in the same area, he will receive an alert and UMa will suggest alternate areas and/or activities.

The Trip Planner's key feature is the GIS, located on the right-hand side of the screen. It displays a map of the park, which displays park areas and day trip areas. The map is continuously updated with booking information. For example, when a user selects a date, the map displays all available park areas, and UMa generates a list of available activities within those areas. Each area has a pre-defined limit as to the number of visitors it can accommodate in any given time period. Users can select single or multiple-day trips, consisting of up to five activities for each day. We are currently working on including wildlife activity and weather warnings into the system.

Insight into use density assists teachers with scheduling and helps them anticipate and proactively plan their groups' use by making transparent potential conflicts with other human or ecosystem stakeholders and known hazards.

UMa also models ethical stewardship. Drawn from academic research, parks management practice, and educational strategies, bio-physical, socio-cultural and visitor experience sustainability indicators and materials specific to regions have been developed. This information can be used as instructional resources, as 'visit conduct' guidelines to share with groups prior to visits, or as an administrative support to educators.

The web resource concept was also designed to engage user groups in participatory stewardship by providing opportunities for groups to form and submit or exchange post-visit descriptive information (i.e., narrative, photos, trail guides with GIS data points). This submission capability might also be utilized to dynamically cue parks staff to novel, emerging or persistent issues observed or experienced by the visitors.

We chose the framework of rich-prospect browsing (Ruecker, 2003), where some meaningful representation of every item in a collection is combined with emergent tools for manipulating a display, as the optimal framework for UMA's design and programming. Geographic information systems that show data plotted on maps are an example of prospect, since they provide the user with a means of seeing an overview that is meaningful. These systems become rich-prospect when the maps are combined with tools that allow the users to manipulate the data that is shown, whether by grouping it, sorting it, or watching its progression over time. Ideally, each data point should be easily understood in its own right, and should also serve as a link to further information.

As we appreciated the complexity of the goal of fostering stewardship, of the competing agendas in the natural environment and of the tensions and interrelationships that require attention in the seemingly simple decision process of planning a visit to the park, adopting the rich-prospect browsing as a design strategy, we hypothesize, will further mitigate the issues of coping and provide an improved opportunity to engage in sustainable decision-making before, during, and following the park visit by virtue alone of diminishing potential emotional triggers.

Interestingly, as with the action research paradigm, rich-prospect browsing is also an apt metaphor for the viewer and user-centric emphasis of the project and is contributing to user studies and on-going prototype improvements throughout the draft and redrafts of the interface design, an important foundation for our methods.

Home
My profile
About the trip planner
Kananaskis country

1. Trips
2. Schedule
3. Maps
4. Forms
5. Resources
6. Book trip

SCHEDULE

CONTINUE

For each day of your trip, please select the location(s) for your visit and the activities you're planning to engage in.

CHANGE DATES

▼ Tuesday SELECT BY AREA SELECT BY ACTIVITY

- Bike
 - Area 1
 - Area 3
 - Area 4
- Hike
- Equestrian
- Snowshoe
- Ski

► Wednesday SELECT BY AREA SELECT BY ACTIVITY

CONTINUE

Figure 2: The second step in the *Trip Planning* process.

Conclusion and Future Research

Helping to manage the potential emotional responses of stakeholders is a challenge for the design process of any system that involves frequent use by a range of different kinds of groups with very different expectations and responses to risk. In the case of natural heritage parks, not only the people involved, but also the environment, needs to be considered as a factor in planning.

Clearly, people will be the ones to interact with an online system, but the kinds of choices they make and how they construe their activities can have profound consequences for other people and for the natural heritage site. We believe that treating the design challenge as a form of action research, with collaborative participation from all stakeholders or their representatives, is an approach that can lead not only to a successful outcome for the design, but also to new insights into the kinds of factors that need to be taken into consideration. Our next phases will continue this process as we turn our attention from trip planning to other aspects of parks management and use.

It is anticipated that data, information and outcomes from the resource will improve management and stewardship objectives by (1) improving knowledge about large group use and its effects, (2) making management implications and decisions increasingly strategic, and (3) forming the basis for the development of educational materials and opportunities that will inform, inspire, and involve Albertans and other visitors in sustainable decision-making in our provincial parks.

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